

Harley Davidson Motorcycles Sales

[Name of the Writer]

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Speaker Notes

Introduction

Harley-Davidson, Inc. came into being in the year 1903. The head quarter of the company is located in Milwaukee, Wisconsin. This company manufactures and sells cruiser class and heavyweight motorcycles. In addition to this, the company supports its clients with motorcycle accessories, parts and other relevant financial services. The company is operating its business in two segments that are financial services and motorcycles and related products. Manufacturing, designing and sales of heavy weight touring, performance and custom motorcycles are included in the segment of Motorcycles and Related Products.

One of the most iconic symbols of American lifestyle is the Harley-Davidson motorcycle. For over 100 years, the large motorcycles, with their distinctive design and customization have been a fixture on highways. Clubs and events organized by HOGs (Harley Owner Groups) have created a loyal community in many countries. The customers of Harley-Davidson see it as an iconic American brand with a rich history and a unique brand heritage. Customers are fascinated by the “look, sound, feel” of a Harley-Davidson and the timeless classical design cues which not only is constant but evolving with innovation.

From its inception, Harley Davidson has enjoyed success in most of North America. Harley Davidson has not been as successful abroad, particularly in Europe and Asia. Harley Davidson also faces fierce competition in Europe and Asia, primarily from manufacturers such as Honda, Kawasaki, Yamaha, Suzuki and BMW. These manufacturers produce a variety of motorcycles that draw consumers away from Harley Davidson. Since 1998 however, Harley

Davidson has increased its market shares in both of these regions. Harley Davidson has also increased its brand recognition abroad. Harley Davidson is now selling police motorcycles to 45 different countries around the world.

The Harley Davidson Company is continuously struggling to gain its customers in order to gain competitive advantage within the market. In order to do this, the company is committed to target younger generation by manufacturing V-Rod motor cycle. With the help of this targeting strategy, the Harley Davidson Company has carved out its strong and dominant position in today's marketplace. With the help of concentrated target marketing approach, the company is gaining its potential customers by targeting the younger demographic of the market. The introduction of the V-Rod is also appealing first time buyers of Harley Davidson motorcycles. Thus, concentrated target marketing approach is pulling new clients towards its dominant brand and high quality motorcycles.

Agenda

- Hypothesis
 - H₀: There is a correlation in sales increase (DV) based on summer season (IV).
 - H_a: There is a correlation in sales increase (DV) based on winter season (IV).
- Source Articles
- Research Process
- Research Results
- Challenges, Implications, and Recommendations
- Conclusion

Conclusion

From the above conclusion, it can be said that there is a strong correlation in sales increase (DV) based on summer season (IV). Summer proves to be a good time for Harley Davidson as the company experiences increase in sales in many regions of the world. It can be said in the end that Harley-Davidson is quite different from other motorcycle brands in that Harley-Davidson broadens the interactions among riders, creates bonds among customers as HOG provides occasions for owners to interact at events or programs for members to enjoy the unique riding experience and kinship. All the factors will continue for creating a strong brand association between the customers and Harley Davidson Company.

References

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